

INTERPRETATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TEACHER AND STUDENT IN FOLK LEGENDS

Erkinova Madinakhon Umid kizi
Alisher Navoi Tashkent State University
of Uzbek Language and Literature
2nd year student
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15666049>

Abstract: This study is devoted to examining the artistic interpretation in folklore of Mir Alisher Navoi, the sultan of the realm of ghazals, and Sultan Husayn Bayqara, a prominent representative of the Timurid dynasty and patron of science and culture. It analyzes how these two figures live on in the people's memory and are reflected through legends and myths created about them.

Keywords: Khorasan, head, sword, ambassador, nightingale, tradition, friendship.

Annotation: This study is dedicated to exploring the artistic interpretation of Mir Alisher Navoi, the sultan of the ghazal domain, and Sultan Husayn Bayqaro, the illustrious representative of the Timurid dynasty and patron of science and culture, in folk oral art. It analyzes how these two figures endure in the people's memory and are portrayed in the legends and myths created about them.

Keywords: Khorasan, head, sword, ambassador, nightingale, tradition, friendship.

History, by informing about events that have taken place over centuries and about the lives and activities of great personalities, brings the future face to face with the past. It encourages the younger generation to look deeply at their history and the glorious lives of their ancestors. In this sense, one of the tasks facing today's literary studies and historical science is to study the relationship between two great personalities - Alisher Navoi and Husayn Bayqaro, who made worthy contributions to the history of Turkic peoples, particularly to the development of their literature, and to determine their contributions to the spiritual, educational, and socio-political life of the Khorasan state.

The relationship between Alisher Navoi and Husayn Bayqaro attracted the attention of scholars, historians, and literary critics even in their own time. Whether the cooperation between these two figures is examined in the form of socio-political interstate relations, based on the relationship between the two statesmen as king and vizier, or based on the connections between two creative individuals and refined poets, there are still many aspects that need to be researched. Therefore, there is a need to study the artistic interpretation of Alisher Navoi and Husayn Bayqaro in examples of oral folk art - epics, legends, and fairy tales - from the perspective of literary studies.

The relationship between Alisher Navoi and Husayn Bayqara attracted the attention of scholars, historians, and literary scholars even in its time. Whether the cooperation between these two figures is examined in the form of socio-political interstate relations, based on the relations between the two statesmen, the king and the vizier, or based on the connections between the two creative individuals and refined poets, there are still many aspects that need to be researched. Therefore, there is a need to study the issue of the artistic interpretation of

the image of Alisher Navoi and Husayn Bayqara in examples of oral folk art - epics, legends, fairy tales - in the aspect of literary studies.

We know that "literary types and genres have emerged as important units in the science of poetics." [6; 15].

"The genre of legend plays an important role in historical prose. A legend is a story told orally. Its emergence and historical foundations are among the most ancient examples of intangible cultural heritage in folklore." [1; 109].

In 1991, the book "If One Speaks of the People, It's Navoi" reflecting the activities of Alisher Navoi and Husayn Bayqara was published. The publisher was Mamatqul Jo'rayev. "This collection contains folk legends about the sultan of world poetry, our ancestor Hazrat Mir Alisher Navoi, who wrote dozens of great and eternal works in our Turkic language. This book was prepared as a gift for the 550th anniversary of the birth of our great scholar." [5; 2]. The book consists of three sections titled "Alisher and the Nightingale," "Quick-witted Mirali," "The Qualities of Blessed Mirali," and seventy-two legends.

The plot structure of the legend genre is distinctive, built on the basis of short and concise interconnected events. The legend genre is distinguished from other genres by indicating an indefinite time through phrases such as "One day" or "In the past." [1; 111].

In legends found in literary-historical works, historical reality and truth are reflected. While legends are based on historical events, they imply that the events described occurred in the past, in a distant historical period. A legend is a special genre that narrates known facts and historically real events. Its epic events are complete and well-rounded. [1; 112].

The book "If One Speaks of the People, It's Navoi" contains legends related to Navoi's wisdom and Husayni's bravery. One of them is the legend "Head and Sword." This legend acknowledges that Alisher Navoi and Husayn Bayqara were very close friends since childhood, that they studied together at school, that they had an extremely sharp-minded teacher, and how the teacher tried to discover what interested these two students. In this legend, let's focus on how the great teacher determined the level of intelligence of his students and what talents and abilities they possessed:

"One day, he (i.e., the teacher) wanted to know his students' intelligence and what they were interested in, so he drew pictures of a head and a sword for both of them and asked them to write a commentary.

Alisher wrote a ghazal praising the head and mind, wisdom. Husayn Bayqara, however, praised the sword and wrote a hymn about battle.

The teacher read the commentaries and, pointing to the sun shining in the sky for Alisher, and to the dark cloud for Husayn Mirza, said to Alisher: "Bravo!" [5; 4].

Through his deep thoughts and acumen, the teacher thus discerns his students' abilities and interests. The reader of this narrative, seeing that Alisher Navoi composed a ghazal based on an image, will recognize his talent for literature and poetry from childhood, while Husayn Bayqara's anthem about battle reveals his aptitude for kingship, military leadership, rulership, and sovereignty.

"The system of characters in legends primarily consists of two or three types. The first includes leading characters, the second supporting characters, and the third rival characters." [1; 115].

The book "If the people speak of Navoi" contains several narratives celebrating the friendship between Alisher Navoi and Husayn Bayqaro. Among them, we can include legends such as "A good person leaves a garden" and "The poet's bridle-holder."

Through the story "A good person leaves a garden," we once again witness Alisher Navoi's wisdom, diligence, and concern for the well-being of others. The narrative begins by describing how Husayn Bayqara, bored from sitting in the palace and having not heard from Mir Alisher for a long time, went to his neighborhood to see his friend. At this time, Navoi was engaged in gardening work.

"From the perspective of the narrative genre, it expresses literary and artistic features. It can be said that legends are formed not on the basis of real-life fiction, but on the foundation of artistic creation." [1; 139].

Uzbek folk proverbs, sayings, and expressions, widespread in our literature, embody centuries of life experience and spiritual values. The expression "A good person leaves a garden" in the legend is also one of the sayings of folk oral tradition with deep philosophical meaning. Through this phrase, Alisher Navoi emphasizes that the virtues and good deeds of every person do not go to waste, and that the people around them and the whole society benefit from their fruits.

"By their nature, legends serve to convey historical evidence, information, or news related to historical events or figures. Important judgments and conclusions about historical and life events that should be passed down to generations remain as historical truth within the content of legends. The roots of legends, deeply embedded in history, not only grow in the period of their creation but also continue to develop and acquire new meanings and content in subsequent stages of the historical and literary process." [1; 140].

Through the parable "A good person leaves a garden," we understand that a good person benefits society through their virtuous deeds, the love and affection they show to others, and the positive impact they have on people. Their good deeds are never forgotten, as each virtuous act benefits many people over time, resulting in numerous rewards for these individuals - a connection to eternity. Therefore, for a person to leave behind a good name, they must perform beneficial and virtuous deeds not only for themselves but also for others. Indeed, the seed of goodness will inevitably grow into a fruitful garden tomorrow.

In conclusion, Alisher Navoi and Husayn Bayqara are highly esteemed as historical figures deeply rooted in folklore, ingrained in the national consciousness and spirit. They were perceived by the people not only as historical figures but also as symbols of justice, wisdom, and humanism. The legends, myths, and narratives created about them reflect the life values, thoughts, dreams, and hopes of our people. In these examples of oral folk art, historical truth is harmoniously blended with artistic imagination. Today, the mutual friendship of these two great personalities and their respect for knowledge and literature are passed down from generation to generation through folklore, inspiring young people to pursue goodness, remain loyal to the Motherland, and serve in the name of knowledge and justice. Therefore, the role of Alisher Navoi and Husayn Bayqara in folklore is not only historical but also educational, spiritual, and cultural in significance.

References:

1. Abdullayeva M. Adabiy-tarixiy asarlarda kichik janrlar poetikasi. –Samarqand: 2021. –B. 274.
2. Jo'rayev M. El desa Navoiyni. –Toshkent: Cho'lpon, 1991. –160b.
3. Jo'raqulov U. A. Navoiy "Xamsa"sida xronotop poetikasi. F.f.d. Dis. Aftoref. –Toshkent: 2017. –B. 15.
4. Quronov D. Adabiyotshunoslikka kirish. –Toshkent: Abdulla Qodiriy nomidagi xalq merosi nashriyoti, 2004. –B. 143.

